

Developing of Learning Resources Leader on Producing and Transforming Phak-waan Tree for Self-Reliance of Lao-Sadue Isan Phak Waan Pah

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Learning Resources Leader, Producing and Transforming Pak-wan Products, Long-life Learning, Self-Reliance, Learning by Doing</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5140148</p>	<p><i>The purposes of the study were 1) to develop leaders in producing and transforming Pak-wan products to have trademark number from Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public Health, 2) to promote Small and Micro Community Enterprises (SMCE) of Lao-Sadue Isan Phak Waan Pah, 3) to promote analyzing of the nutrition of Pak-wan components and Food Patent for Phak-waan tea, 4) to compare learning achievement score of pretest and posttest, 5) to assess the quality of pre and post of doing projects on the Small and Micro Community Enterprises (SMCE), and 6) to find the set of learning management, agriculture network and Pak-wan knowledge. The sample groups were 8 groups of Lao-Sadue Isan Phak Waan Pah. The research instruments were 1) the Manual of producing and transforming Pak-wan drink, 10 steps of producing and packaging Pak-wan tea, and plans from Pak-wan tea, 2) tools for collecting data; achievement test, the Quality Assessment Form of the Small and Micro Community Enterprises (SMCE), the questionnaire on satisfaction of attending workshop and, 3) the statistic used were average, mean, standard deviation, t-test and defective index. The results found that 1) the supply for developing Pak-wan company was successful and the food patent was no. 44-2-00664 which allowed on April 7, 2021, 2) ways to improve members including observing and doing workshops on producing and transforming Pak-wan tea at 88.94/83.22, the effectiveness index at 0.6667, 3) the assessment on the quality of the Small and Micro Community Enterprises (SMCE) of Lao-Sadue Isan Phak Waan Pah significantly at 0.01, 4) having trademark named "Phak-waan Pah Palang Song Cha-nid Song" or "Double Energy from Pak-wan tea" no. 44-2-00664-2-0001 on May 13, 2021, and 5) 11 topics of agriculture networks, and online learning on Pak-wan plaiting.</i></p>

Introduction

Hence Northeastern University has been focused on educational institutes and communities of Ban Kwao village and Ban Kwao Bueng Kui at Maha Sarakham province for a while, this could make communities' leaders, knowledgeable people, and principals realized on their communities, schools and communities that they haven't participatory for a while.

According to their duties, there were not chances to share or discuss about their communities' problems which was lacking of the learning centers, especially Pak-wan Pha learning center. Hence, this center lacked of the specialists, lacked of well management, lacked of expenditure and also visitor's area. Ban Lao Sub-district Municipality was interested in doing the research and development, so there was an aim to develop leaders' qualities and villagers' skills to promote the center as leaning management and emphasizing on using the area worthy. Moreover, the aim of the research was to promote the center as well as the self-reliance learning center over the philosophy of Sufficiency Economy. Leaders and teachers in Ban Kwao Sadue Isan, Ban Kwao Bueng Kui, Ban Lao Municipality and the social welfare were aware that this should have learning centers for offering families, communities, and organizations which would be new economy in Kwao and Bueng Kui communities. Moreover, the project could enhance abilities of the people in this area, inherit ancestors' wisdom, have community and school's identity, and preserve and develop continuously (Sanyen, interviewed September 1, 2017).

As Chantarasombat (2011, p. 152) mentioned that there was a research and development emphasizing on practicing and using participatory method which could support leaders' reliability in fixing poverty, developing society, and having good health. Then applied this action learning with individual, family, and groups of leaders of the project. The study was the action research or the Participatory Action Research relevant to academic leaders, skillful people who could turn to be the experts later. Moreover, this should have the

participatory action research in communities and schools for developing sufficiency economy learning center appropriately. In communities of Wang-Chan, all 3 villages in Nakha sub-district, Wapi Pathum district, Maha Sarakham province became the innovative villages where fixing the poverty concretely. In 2019, Northeastern University did a research named “Developing Learning Resources Leaders in Learning Phak-Waan Pah for Self-Reliance through Sufficiency Economy by Using Participatory Action Research in Ban Kwao, Lao Sub-District, Kosumphisai District, Maha Sarakham Province. The participants were 8 people from Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah at Ban Wang Yai, Wang Yai sub-district, Wang Yai district, Khon Kaen province, and 7 people from Wang Yai Jai Ka-set. These 2 groups caused to have community enterprises on Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah and Wang Yai Jai Ka-set Phak Waan Pah transforming.

According to Covid 2019, the researcher, the co-researcher, and the team were interested in studying developing learning resources leaders on Phak-Waan Pah for self-reliance. The participants were from Lao Sa Due Isan Pak Wan who were prepared to do the research and development about producing and transforming Pak Wan tea. The study was done for having the approval allowance from Food through the action learning in the form of STEM and the Research and Development but using the participatory action research from Kosum Phisai Agricultural Extension Office, Maha Sarakham Provincial Public Health Office, the faculty of Education, the faculty of Engineer at Northeastern University, and 8 people in the area. These participatory was made for increasing levels of learning center, increasing learning conditions, needs, and subjects in order to analyze the communities’ problems at Ban Kwao, Lao sub-district, Kosum Phisai district, Maha Sarakham province. The data from the study were surveyed and interviewed by the researcher, co-researcher, and students in order to collect the data from the current conditions.

Background

Jennex, Olfman (2005) defines KM as the practice of selectively applying from previous experiences of decision making to current and future decision to current activities with the express of improving the organization’s effectiveness. Also, Chantarasombat, Srisa-ard, Kuofie & Jennex (2010), KM is seen as a way of changing the traditional knowledge transfer process to something that assist who remain in the village. The KM approach investigated consisted of five stages: 1) Preparation 2) Create motivation, promote participation 3) Develop the KM plan 4) Implement the KM plan, and 5) Evaluation. Jennex (2013) defined knowledge management success and dimensions measures of the organizations can use to value knowledge management success. Besides that, an unclear unitarily engineering organization is used to illustrate how these dimensions and measures can be used to demonstrate the success of knowledge management initiative/project. Managing the life cycle of knowledge, Global organization Ramazanzade, Aati, Shokohifard & Farshid (2019) stated that pedagogical knowledge management is the management of knowledge and experiences in teaching, assessment, learning theories, classroom management, and other areas of education. An analytical study of the literature can be helpful in understanding the pedagogical knowledge management approach. Thus, this study aims to perform a synthesis research on the efficacy of pedagogical knowledge management and to explain its applications and strategies.

Donn (2006) defines urbanization and sustainability in Asia as the plasticenes of the cased studies. They are also classified under brad field’s or heading for systematically documenting, comparing and deriving lessons of good practice for sustainable urban development. Each good practice was assessed the case studies of 12 Asian countries: good governance in proved urban management, effective and efficient infrastructure and service provision, financing and cost recovery, social and environmental sustainability, innovation change and revering, and international development assistance. The case studies, for example, found in Thailand were: 1) Muang Klaeng municipality on sustainable city inventiveness, 2) Phichit municipality on waste recycling, and 3) Songkla municipality on waste management and education.

Chantarasombat & Agsonsua (2021, p.234) there should be ongoing, participatory action research with the target community for at least 1 year. An extended research period will increase the efficiency of the development guidelines and processes. It will also reveal the development at the household level and at the group level of a learning community with follow-ups and ongoing reflections to improve the process. The local administrative organizations of Kosum Phisai District (Maha Sarakham Province), and Wang Yai sub-district administration organization, Waeng Yai District (Khon Kaen Province) should support ongoing research projects for to select a suitable research area in the academic year 2020.

Research Questions

1. How did the current conditions, problems, and needs of producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah find occur or how did the researcher find the cooperation from the supporters?
2. How did the researcher define names for the innovative product and Pak wan tea in the form of hermetically sealed container?
3. What effectiveness from analyzing the using of products and transforming Phak Waan Pah for self-reliance?

4. Which criteria would be used to assess the quality of Lao Sa Due Phak Waan Pah community enterprise?

Purposes of the Study

1. To develop leaders in producing and transforming Pak-wan products to have trademark license from Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public Health
2. To promote Small and Micro Community Enterprises (SMCE) of Lao-Sadue Isan Pak Wan Pha in the form of hermetically sealed container 2.5 g.
3. To promote nutrition analyzing of Pak-wan components and trademark for Pak-wan tea
4. To compare learning achievement score of pretest and posttest of leaders to find E1 and E2, the effective index of learning center, and the satisfaction of studying and practicing ways to produce and transform Pak Wan tea
5. To assess the quality of pre and post doing projects on the Small and Micro Community Enterprises (SMCE)
6. To find the set of learning management, agriculture network and Pak-wan knowledge

Scopes of the Study

According to the project management for developing learning resources leaders in learning Pak-Wan Pha for Self-Reliance through Sufficiency Economy research and development which focusing on participatory action research, this type of research was the Inside Out type which used to encourage the community management on self-management, used to create skills of making relationships, and used to have well management. These guided to have self-reliance on getting to know ourselves, knowing resources, and knowing how to increase the resources value to have leading, supply, and administration supply effectively. Meanwhile, there was a condition for learning in finding demand directly by using the action learning and participatory action research and also the Northeastern university experts were attended. There were 9 steps of participatory action research; 1) preparing the team for doing project of planting Pak Wan, 2) analyzing possibilities, 3) studying current conditions, problems, needs in developing the target group, 4) analyzing data, 5) doing plan of participatory, 6) following and developing plans, 7) developing quality and increasing levels of knowledge, 8) following and assessing, and 9) making conclusion and sharing knowledge. These conceptual frameworks were from these theorists;

Srisa-ad (2006, p.41) stated that model was the structure of showing relationships between components which the researcher could explain relationships occurring naturally or systematically. Atsawaphume (2000, p.15) suggested 4 ways to investigate development patterns; 1) studying related knowledge, 2) defining principles and patterns components, 3) drafting patterns, and 4) examining and finding appropriate possibilities. Chantarasombat (2008, p. 192-195) defined 5 steps of learning through practicing; 1) setting challenge conditions to have learning opportunities, 2) doing a participatory plan, 3) following plan and improving plan, 4) making conclusion and giving feedback, and 5) sharing knowledge, and Chantarasombat (2021, p. 55) defined 6 steps of action learning through practicing; 1) identity task & learning opportunity 2) studying problem/need 3) planning together 4) doing & improving 5) reflecting community enterprise indicators and 6) Sharing the learning.

From the scope of the study and research theories, the study was the participatory action research. The conceptual framework was shown in Figure 1 below;

from Northeastern University, on field researchers, local experts who were focusing on practicing, learning and doing research.

- 1.2 There were 4 ways for developing the innovative learning; 1) lessons of developing learning resources leaders in learning how to produce and transform Phak-Waan Pah tea for Self-Reliance, 2) a manual for planting, producing and transforming Phak-Waan Pah tea for Self-Reliance, 3) indicators for the community enterprise in Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah, and 4) sets of learning how to plant and take care of Phak Waan Pahon the agriculture networks and online knowledge.

2. Variables

2.1 Independent Variable

- 1) Learning resources leaders
- 2) Drafting of producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah
- 3) Types of producing and transforming products

2.2 Dependent Variable

- 1) Learning achievement and effective index of the learning resources leaders in producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah tea
- 2) The place for producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah and trademark license from Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public Health
- 3) Results from analyzing properties of Phak Waan Pah and the approve for food patent number
- 4) Buying 2 types of Phak Waan Pah in the sealed container and names of the products from the Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public Health

3. Research Instruments

3.1 Instruments for Developing Works

- 1) The manual of learning resources leaders in learning how to plant, produce, and transform Phak Waan Pah tea for Self-Reliance with the philosophy of sufficiency economy
- 2) Lessons for developing learning resources leaders in learning how to produce and transform Phak-Waan Pah tea for Self-Reliance
- 3) Indicators of the community enterprise in Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah
- 4) Drafting of producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah

3.2 Instruments for Collecting Data

- 1) 3 achievement tests, and each test included 20 questions, and totally 60 questions. The tests comprised; 1) knowledge management test, 2) self-reliance test, and 3) learning resource test
- 2) Rubric Scores were used for assessing learning resources leaders in levels of family and network
- 3) Assessment form of the indicators included 7 parts of learning resources and 44 indicators applying from Kosum Phisai Agricultural Extension Office
- 4) The questionnaire on satisfaction, comprehension, practicing, and applying in training and seminar

Data Collection

The authors acquired theoretical knowledge by pre-test and post-test learning scores from the learning achievement test. They collected the learning retention data after the pre-test and the post-test, which was performed two weeks after, and the satisfaction data by the satisfaction questionnaire.

Data Analysis

1) The efficiency and effectiveness of the learning module were analyzed by using the Mean and Percentage of Brahmawong (1994). The efficiency was searched for using E1/ E2 formula, as follows:

$$E_1 = \frac{\sum X/N}{A} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{\sum F/N}{B} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

The effectiveness index of the learning module was analyzed by using the following E.I. formula

$$\text{Effectiveness Index (E.I.)} = \frac{\text{The sum of the post-test score} - \text{The Sum of the pre-test score}}{\text{(Student number X full score) - The Sum of the pre-test score}}$$

2) The student's knowledge and learning retention data was collected by pre-test and post-test learning score of the learning achievement test while the learning retention had to be collected after the post-test.

Comparison of the learning achievement of the learning module was analyzed by mean (\bar{X}) standard deviation (SD), values of t-test (dependent), and comparative analysis between pre-test and post-test (Sri sa-ard, 2006).

3) The satisfaction on the learning module was collected by using the satisfaction questionnaire. It was analyzed by using the mean value (\bar{X}) and standard deviation (SD) for measuring the satisfaction level.

Research Procedure

There were 14 activities in the participatory action research; 1) studying the sufficiency economy center for self-reliance to fix the poverty by Mr. Sutas Upontian at Maha Sarakham, 2) studying possibilities of successful indicators and writing project, 3) preparing the progress of doing project, 4) having a meeting for interpreting understanding, 7) having a meeting for practicing/ training speakers, 8) having data for planting Phak Waan Pah in communities, 9) preparing stage of the master plan and indicators for self-reliance with the philosophy of sufficiency economy; poverty fixing, social development and good health, 10) offering stage for discussing integrations on learning resources leaders in learning how to plant Phak Waan Pah for fixing poverty's problems in communities, 11) following and supporting plans for enhancing learning resource leaders in learning to grow Phak Waan Pah for self-reliance, 12) training, 13) assessing pre and post developing, and 14) in phase 1 of 2019, preparing stage for making conclusion and presenting learning resource leaders in learning to grow Phak Waan Pah for self-reliance, and in phase 2 of 2020 creating network for learning resource leaders in learning to grow Phak Waan Pah for self-reliance.

Conclusion

1) Creating and developing the place for producing and transforming Phak Waan tea size 6 m × 12 m by fixing it 3 times. This fixing was approved by the committee from Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public Health in Maha Sarakham in March 23, 2021. After that, the team asked for having the license from Food and Drug Administration and finally the team got trademark no. 44-2-00664 which been on April 7, 2021. The team could produce and sell both 2 types of Phak Waan Pah tea.

2) Getting workshop on producing and transforming food in sealed container named "Phak Waan Pah Palang Song" or "Double Power of Phak Waan Pah" and studying on agriculture community enterprise from the group of Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah by using the manual of learning.

2.1 Learning resources leaders in learning ways to produce and transform Phak-Waan Pah Palang Song, E1 was 88.94 and E2 was 83.22, the effective index was 0.6667. This meant the leaders in this learning center gained more knowledge 66.67.

2.2 The achievement score of the post test was higher significantly at 0.01.

2.3 The satisfaction of the leaders was at the highest level.

2.4 There were 10 steps of producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah Palang Song (January 1, 2021 – March 31, 2021)

Step 1: Choosing fresh leaves from 1 kilogram of Pak Wan

Step 2: Cleaning fresh leaves from step 1 in stainless trash 2 times

Step 3: Drying fresh leaves till they were almost dry

Step 4: Splitting Pak Wan leaves into very small pieces

Step 5: Then frying leaves for 1 hour till they were dried and had a nice smell

Step 6: Baking the fried leaves for 1 hour in order to get rid of the humidity and fungi

Step 7: Spinning those baked leaves till they turned to be the powder

Step 8: Then containing the powder of Phak Waan Pah into a bag, 2.5 kgs each, and sealed

those bags

Step 9: Then packing the products by foil pouches and make sure that they were not opened. After that, put them into the big boxes. There were 2 sizes of the boxes; 50 grams for 20 plastic bags and 25 grams for 10 plastic bags.

Step 10: Selling the products

3) There were 4 steps of analyzing properties of Phak Waan Pah and ways to get trademark license of hermetically sealed container; 1) designing the signal of the product, 2) choosing the standard box for carrying the bags of tea which could keep products for 6 months at least, 3) adding how to make a drink from tea, and 4) showing the brochure of trademark number.

4) The group of community enterprise Lao Sa Due Isan followed the plan of the research project "Developing of Learning Resources Leader on Producing and Transforming Pak-wan Tree for Self-Reliance of Lao-Sadue Isan Phak Waan Pah by using the participatory action research technique and this group was evaluated to find the potential of community enterprise;

4.1 The comparison of the potential of the group after progressing was higher significantly at 0.01

4.2 The potential of the group after progressing was averagely at high level (\bar{X} = 2.94,

SD = 0.25). When considering 7 parts, the average was at high level as follow; 1) results from community enterprise (\bar{X} =3.00, SD = 0.00), 2) product and service management Mean=3.00, SD = 0.00), 3) member administration in community enterprise (\bar{X} =2.96, SD=0.25), 6) planning for community enterprise (\bar{X} =2.89, SD= 0.29), and knowledge management (\bar{X} =2.83, SD = 0.23).

5. When analyzing nutrition of Phak Waan Pah, most of them had large and small leaves, for example, KK63/04689-001 reported on September 23, 2020 Report No. TRKK63/13602 PM-QP-24-01-001-R03 (12/11/61) P2/2-KK. These made the committee from Food and Drug Ministration, Ministry of Public Health in Maha Sarakham accepted that properties of Pak Wan tea benefit for bones, eyes and bod which had high nutrition value at 100 gram including 1) calcium 6185 mg/kg can decrease risky of having osteoarthritis, 2) phosphorus 1295 mg/kg can make your eyes brighter, 3) vitamin A (B-Carotene) * 247.23 can boost energy, and 4) vitamin B3 (Vitamin B3 (Niacin)) * can low your cholesterol.

6. Knowledge were managed as growing, preserving, and transforming tea. This could offer 11 sets of online knowledge through <https://www.facebook.com>; 1) condensing the branches of Phak Waan to have root faster, 2) ways to keep Phak Waan correctly, 3) grafting, and choosing branches of Pak Wan to have root faster, 4) having experiences to grow Phak Waan effectively, 5) how to condense Pak wan effectively, 6) Pak Wan diseases and how to protect form diseases, 7) plants that can grow with Pak Wan, 8) ways to collect Pak Wan correctly in order to have new leaves faster, 9) growing Pak Wan from condensing, 10) how to buy grafts of Phak Waan to grow well 100 %, and 11) growing Phak Waan Pah with another plants.

Discussion

From the research “Developing of Learning Resources Leader on Producing and Transforming Phak-waan Tree for Self-Reliance of Lao-Sadue Isan Phak Waan Pah”, there were some issues found;

1. Building and developing the place for producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah which followed the engineer design and experts’ advices from Food and Drug Administration, Ministry of Public Health could be successful in 6 months relevant to the scopes of times. Moreover, there were possibilities for building comprising the budget, building process, and quality of building. This project could work well because it was about the participatory between the researcher, and the team from the Agricultural Extension Office at Kosum Phisai, and pharmacists from Food and Drug Administration, and also the group of Lao Sa Due Isan. The aim of the project was to build and develop place for Phak Waan Pah which using budget totally cost 250,000 baths. Besides that, the project supported on; analyzing Pak Wan Pha nutrition 16,200 baths, using the groundwater from Ban Kwao Sa Due Isan for producing Phak Waan tea 6,900, developing producing room 10,000 baths, having Certificate of Manufacturer 4,000 baths, and having food patent 2,000 baths. Furthermore, after making conclusion of the project, there was reliability to have participatory and self-reliance relevant to Chantarasombat (2006, p.106-109) who stated that networking in community for self-reliance in sub-district and villages could have purposes, visions, plans, activities, practicing, observing, improving, and reflecting which should be considering to 1) creating changed leaders, 2) creating and developing networks, and communities, and 3) creating ways to adapt the researcher’s role, developers, and practicing researchers.

2. The potential from 8 leaders was effective to the process of the knowledge effectively at 88.94/83.22 which higher than 80/80, and the effective index was 0.6667. This meant the leaders gained more knowledge 66.67 % and the satisfaction of the leaders was at the highest level (\bar{X} =4.38, SD = 0.26). That was because 1) leaders were interesting and be required for the members in Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah community enterprise because they gave them knowledge about how to gain more income from Phak Waan Pah. They prepared the place for producing and transforming Phak Waan Pah. From analyzing examining Phak Waan Pah in the laboratory in Khon Kaen, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives, there were participatory, sharing knowledge, and also be the speakers for the leaders and agricultural model in fixing poverty and having self-reliance. Mr. Sutas Upon-tian was approved from the product standard certification on good agricultural practices for food crop $\text{พ.ร.บ.} 9001-2556$, approval no. $\text{พ.บ.} 03-9001-37441234371$, conversion no. 440309-9371-0001-0368, Type: Phak Waan Pah, in the area of 2 Rais (3,200 square meters), located in Moo 8, Lao sub-district, Kosum Phisai district, Maha Sarakham, approved on August 7, 2019, expired on August 6, 2021, 2) this producing and transforming Pak Wan tea was relevant to members’ need on having agricultural laboratory, 3) Debt-Free Agriculture Group in Mukdahan, Na-Srinuan, Muang district, Mukdahan province was the first community enterprise which offered the knowledge about producing and transforming Pak Wan tea and also sold them with the food patent no. 49-2-01063-2-0001, 4). Members were reliable to have participatory in working and they would be trained through the approved manual by 5 experts. They concluded that the manual was possible, appropriate and get highest benefits. This related to Chantarasombat and Agsonsua (2020, p. 197-207) and Chantarasombat, & Agsonsua (2021, p. 222) studied the Developing of Learning Resources Leader on Producing and Transforming Pak-wan Tree for Self-Reliance through the philosophy of sufficient economy with the participatory action research. The result found the potential of leaders was effective to the process of the knowledge effectively at 86.59/80.75 and the effective index was 0.6745. This meant the leaders gained more knowledge 67.45 % and the satisfaction of the leaders was at the highest level (\bar{X} =4.35, SD= 0.39).

3. From assessing the community enterprise of Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah through 7 parts, there were standard and 44 indicators from comparing post and preprocessing significantly at 0.01 relevant to Chantarasombat and Agsonsua (2020, p. 208) studied the Developing of Learning Resources Leader on Producing and Transforming Pak-wan Tree for Self-Reliance through the philosophy of sufficient economy significantly at 0.01 and the knowledge management ($\bar{x} = 2.83$, S.D. = 0.23) was averagely at level 3. The leaders from Lao Sa Due Isan Phak Waan Pah had been trained until they could have Smart Farmer Excellence and offering online learning for members (<https://www.facebook.com>) in learning agriculture knowledge in 2020. The lessons included 1) agriculture manual: condensing Pak Wan, 2) agriculture manual: how to collect Phak Waan, 3) agriculture manual: grafting, and choosing branches of Pak Wan to have root faster, 4) agriculture manual: having experiences to grow Phak Waan effectively, 5) agriculture manual: how to condense Phak waan effectively, 6) agriculture manual: Phak Waan diseases and how to protect from diseases, 7) agriculture manual: plants that can grow with Pak Wan, 8) agriculture manual: ways to collect Phak Waan correctly in order to have new leaves faster, 9) agriculture manual: growing Phak Waan from condensing, 10) agriculture manual: how to buy grafts of Phak Waan to grow well 100 %, and 11) agriculture manual: growing Phak Waan Pah with another plants.

4. Phak Waan Pah nutrition, the tea was examined with 2 members and 1 researcher to mix with food. The examiners have osteoarthritis, exhausted, and having high cholesterol. They mixed Phak Waan tea with hot water and leave them 2-3 minutes and then drink it slowly. This experiment was during January 1, 2021 – April 30, 2021. This could say that Phak Waan tea had high nutrition value at 100 gram including 1) calcium 6185 mg/kg can decrease risky of having osteoarthritis, 2) phosphorus 1295 mg/kg can make your eyes brighter, 3) vitamin A (B-Carotene) * 247.23 can boost energy, and 4) vitamin B1(Thiamine) * 0.66373 mg/100 kg can low your cholesterol. Those 3 examiners were changed because the tea can decrease some risky of having osteoarthritis because they could walk well even, they are 69-70 years old (Chantarasombat, interviewed March 1, 2021). Moreover, their blood pressure was lower because their cholesterol was lower.

Since this group produced and transformed Pak wan tea by following these 10 steps: Step 1: Choosing fresh leaves from 1 kilogram of Pak Wan, Step 2: Cleaning fresh leaves from step 1 in stainless trash 2 times, Step 3: Drying fresh leaves till they were almost dry, Step 4: Splitting Pak Wan leaves into very small pieces, Step 5: Then frying leaves for 1 hour till they were dried and had a nice smell, Step 6: Baking the fried leaves for 1 hour in order to get rid of the humidity and fungi, Step 7: Spinning those baked leaves till they turned to be the powder, Step 8: Then containing the powder of Phak Waan Pah into a bag, 2.5 kgs each, and sealed those bags, Step 9: Then packing the products by foil pouches and make sure that they were not opened. After that, put them into the big boxes. There were 2 sizes of the boxes; 50 grams for 20 plastic bags and 25 grams for 10 plastic bags, and Step 10: Selling the products

Moreover, this project can be improved until having trademark named “Phak-waan Pha Palang Song Cha-nid Song” or “Double Energy from Pak-wan tea” no. 44-2-00664-2-0001, English name: PHAK WAAN PAH DRINK OF DOUBLE HIGHQUALITY ENVELOPE TYPE TEA, Food type: the hermetically sealed container (Food and Drug Administration, 2021). Besides that, Lao Sa Due Isan made them publicity.

Suggestions

1. To develop the leaders in this learning center, so it should be more Phak Waan, especially from another village in order to create learning centers and to improve local tourism
2. This tea could be kept for 6 months so this should have lessons for self-learning and making module for learning which is significant. Users should study how to use deliberately and follow them correctly.
3. This should have strategies for creating research and innovations in developing community sustainably and steadily.

Recommendations

1. This should have an innovative research that can enhance the machine for producing, roasting and baking Phak Waan tea. Each time of producing should be in the appropriate time and have the same quality of product. This can occur innovative research STEM Education to use machine besides people.
2. This should have a research that develop the machine for producing Phak Waan tea
3. This should have research clinic in the university in order to work with communities comfortably and can develop community sustainably and stably.
4. This should have drug certificate for Phak Waan Pah which can be useful for the researcher and the community.

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